

Australian Research Data Commons

Australasian Best Practices: Identifiers for Research Organisations and Facilities

V.1.0

By Identifiers for Instruments Australasia (i4iOZ)
for the *Australian Research Data Commons*

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Text & infographics only.

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Purpose

Facilities are key research infrastructures, and accurate standardised identification of them is necessary to contextualise relationships between them and other research entities such as people, data, physical objects, instruments and projects.

This document provides disambiguation, definition, scope and best practice advice for persistent identification of research organisations and research organisational units in Australasia.

This document is an output of the Identifiers for Instruments in Australasia Community of Practice (i4iOZ).

Rationale

PIDs facilitate the linking of research components (instruments, data, people, organisations, funding) with outputs (metadata, publications, data sets, software, workflows, calibrations).

Persistently identifying Facilities addresses a critical gap in the building of an interconnected research data infrastructure landscape.

In general, PID uptake and usage include a range of benefits:

- Improved discoverability and visibility of organisations and their data, published on the web
- Improved connection between data outputs and the organisations that generated them
- Metrics that quantify the use and cost of facilities
- FAIR and CARE compliant metadata and data
- Facilitation of interoperability and open data sharing
- Better Integrity and reproducibility
- Support of appropriate authentication and access to sensitive data
-

Particular benefits of identifying Facilities with a Persistent Identifier include:

- Disambiguation where similar names exist
- Name changes and facility mergers
- Staff recognition via linkages between Orcids and RORs
- Improved awareness of connections between organisations

Scope

The successful identification of facilities requires alignment with broader national and institutional policies. Australia has been a global leader in this area with the release of the "Australian National Persistent Identifier (PID) Strategy and Roadmap" in early 2024. Led by the ARDC, this strategy identifies five priority PIDs:

1. ORCID for identifying researchers and contributors to research
2. ROR for identifying research organisations and organisations that are part of the research ecosystem such as funders or research infrastructure providers
3. DOI for identifying research grants, data, publications, instruments and other types of research outputs in scope for the DOI service provider
4. RAiD for identifying research projects and activities
5. IGSN for identifying research physical samples

Identifier	Identifies	Service/organisational body responsible
ORCID	researchers and contributors to research	AAF/Australian Orcid Consortium
ROR	research organisations and facilities that are part of the research ecosystem	ROR
DOI	research grants, data, publications, instruments and other types of research outputs in scope for the DOI service provider	ARDC DOI service via DataCite
RAiD	research projects and activities	ARDC RAiD Service
IGSN	research physical samples	ARDC DOI Service/ IGSN e.V

This document also draws on the work of the international community via the Research Data Alliance [PIDs for Instruments \(PIDINST\) Working Group](#) and the [FAIR Facilities and Instruments Research Coordination Network](#) in the United States.

Definitions

Current discourse within the Australasian and international communities suggests that a facility is not merely a collection of hardware but an essential research entity that contextualizes instrument use and relationships between other research components.

This guide defines a Facility as a type of Organisation, with the following qualities as per the [Australian PIDS Benchmarking Tool 2025](#):

“A facility enables research by offering specialised equipment, laboratories, computing resources, or experimental environments. A research facility is a physical or virtual resource that supports scientific investigation by providing specialised infrastructure, instruments, and services. Facilities may be dedicated to specific disciplines, such as particle accelerators for physics, sequencing labs for genomics, or high-performance computing clusters for data-intensive research. Access to a facility is typically governed by institutional policies, external partnerships, or funding agreements. “

(2.2.4 Facilities Research Input)

A Research Facility is a specific type of entity and should also not be confused with facilities such as a glass-blowing facility, an animal facility or a faculty facility for example.

Best Practice Recommendations

ROR

The recommended PID for identification of a facility is the [Research Organisation Registry Identifier: ROR](#).

ROR is a global, community-led registry of open persistent identifiers for research organizations. It is designed to be "infrastructure for infrastructure," meaning it is intended for integration into software applications and scholarly metadata by information professionals rather than manual use by individual researchers. ROR is the standard organizational identifier supported in [Crossref](#) DOI metadata, [DataCite](#) DOI metadata, [RAiD](#) metadata and [ORCID](#).

[Version 2 of ROR's metadata schema](#) includes any organization involved in research, and it specifically defines "facility" as a specialized site where research occurs.

ROR Relationships

ROR includes "child" and "related" organizations such as a university's research institutes, hospitals, and laboratories or a multinational company's branches in different countries. This is particularly relevant to the Australian research ecosystem for two reasons:

- University-based and CSIRO-based facilities retain the information on their institutional host in ROR
- NCRIS capabilities often contain nodes based at university or CSIRO. Those facilities can combine the “child” relationship with their host institution and the “related” relationship with the NCRIS capabilities they participate in. The associations with a host institution and a NCRIS capability are not mutually exclusive.

Getting a ROR

Australian organisations can apply for a ROR via the [ROR request Form](#). All requests go through a centralized, community-based curation process and anyone can request additions or updates to the registry.

Updates to RORs can similarly be made via the request form or by contacting the [Identifier Services team at ARDC](#)

For information on use of the ROR API or questions regarding the schema go to [ROR Readme](#) or make contact via [email](#).

Other identifiers

This best practice guide is intended to work as part of the Australian PID Benchmarking strategy and recognises that while ROR is the benchmark for organisational identification, definitions and standards are an evolving space, and more specific terms and identifiers are also useful and appropriate in certain situations.

ABN, ISNI and RRID are three other identifiers in the ecosystem that may be of use.

ABN

[Australian Business Number \(ABN\)](#) can be used for organisations which are registered in Australia, but not primarily research focussed and thus not eligible for a ROR.

ISNI

[The International Standard Name Identifier \(ISNI\)](#) is a general identifier for the public identity of individuals and organisations.

RRID

[Research Resource Identification \(RRIDs\)](#) is a unique persistent identifier originating in the biomedical field and used for citing key research resources

RRIDs often identify a facility as a "resource type" or "input to experiments".

Use cases

Use cases are available at the [i4iOZ website resource page](#)

References

- [*i4iOZ Best Practices: PIDs for Instruments \(1.0\)*](#)
- [*PIDINST Working Group*](#)
- [*Persistent Identification of Instruments White paper*](#)
- [*Recommendations Toward a Framework for Adoption and Use of Persistent Identifiers for Research Facilities, Platforms, and Instruments*](#)
- [*Australian PIDS Benchmarking Tool 2025:*](#)
- [*Use cases as of April 2026*](#)

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